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Pressure Drop in Automotive Particulate Filters

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Introduction

Automotive transportation is ceaselessly expanding. For example, 88,460 vehicles used Czech highway D1 between Spořilov and Chodov in 2010 during one workday.[1] However, the total amount of vehicles in 2016 was 99,265.[2] That means an increase of more than 10,000 vehicles in six years. In connection with that, quantity of emissions released to the atmosphere keeps growing. European Parliament endeavors to reduce impacts of the automotive transportation by tightening up emission standards for new vehicles.

Carbon monoxide (CO), nitric oxide (NO), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) and hydrocarbons (HCs) are dangerous gases which come out of car exhaust systems. Particulates are present in exhaust fumes as well – soot is the main component of particulates. Soot is a mass of carbon; size of its particles is between 10 nm and 10 μm. Particulates are very dangerous because they can get through lungs into blood. On the surface of a particulate, there can be adsorbed other harmful substances, such as residues of fuel, polycyclic hydrocarbons or sulfates.[3] In order to reduce these emissions, catalytic converters and particulate filter are parts of exhaust system. Catalytic converter transforms harmful gases to carbon dioxide and water vapor, particulate filter retains particulates.

Diesel particulate filters (DPFs) are nowadays basic component of vehicles with compression ignition engines. In connection with tightening up the emission standards, gasoline particulate filters become more and more often in vehicles with spark-ignition engines. Particulate filters are usually made from a monolith of a porous material, usually aluminium titanate (Al₂TiO₅, abbreviated as AT), silicon carbide (SiC) or cordierite (2 MgO – 2 Al₂O₃ – 5 SiO₂); the monolith is en-

Figure 1: Sectional view of particulate filter. Yellow – porous walls of channels, black – cement plug, dark blue arrows – exhaust gases with particulates, light blue – exhaust gases without particulates

closed by a steel capsule.[4] The monolith is formed by parallel channels of square cross-section. Each channel is plugged at one end by impermeable cement, so that a typical chessboard structure is created. Passing exhaust fumes are forced to go through a porous wall of the channel; depth filtration occurs here and, when porous wall is clogged, cake filtration occurs as well. A mechanism of the gas flow through the filter is shown in the Figure 1.[5]

Modern particulate filters do not need to be cleaned mechanically. Once they are choked by soot, control unit starts a regeneration process: More carbohydrates from fuel get into the exhaust fumes. HCs are burnt in oxidation catalyst, which warms up the gases to approximately 600 °C (1100 °F), hence the soot is burnt to carbon dioxide and the filter is regenerated.[6]

Particulate filter may reduce environmental strain. On the other hand, it is another expensive component of the vehicle. Furthermore, the filter decreases efficiency of the engine, as it represents an obstacle in the exhaust system, which causes the pressure drop. By decreasing efficiency of the engine, particulate filter increases fuel combustion.

This work studies pressure drop in several different particulate filters and influence of used porous material.

Measuring Apparatus

First of all, it is necessary to cut a cuboid (Figure 2) out of the monolith (Figure 3), so that it fits into the reactor: sizes of each sample are in the Table 1.

Figure 2: Photo of cut sample of particulate filter

Figure 3: Photo of particulate filter monolith

Table 1: Sizes of samples used in the experiment

	aluminium titanate	cordierite	silicon carbide
length (in)	5.5	4.5	5.5
width (in)	1.15	1.15	1.15
height (in)	0.2	0.2	0.2
channels per square inch	350	300	300

Figure 4: Scheme of measuring apparatus. 1 – nitrogen cylinder, 2 – valve, 3 – MFC with control unit, 4 – reactor with sample of filter with thermocouple (T) and pressure gauge (p)

The cut sample is inserted into the reactor, which is then closed and sealed up. A capillary that brings gas is connected to the reactor – thanks to similar properties of gases, we can use nitrogen, which is safe and well-accessible in the laboratory. Between nitrogen cylinder and reactor, there is a valve and a mass flow controller (MFC) with a control unit connected to it. Using the MFC we can control the flow rate of the gas. There is a differential pressure gauge and a thermocouple connected to reactor. The pressure gauge measures the pressure drop before and behind the filter sample. The thermocouple enables measuring of the temperature, however, we do not use it in this experiment. Scheme of the whole system is in the Figure 4.

Figure 5: Graph comparing relations between pressure drops and space velocity. Green – aluminium titanate, red – cordierite, blue – silicon carbide. Connecting line created using quadratic regression

Results

Results of the measuring of all the samples can be seen in the Figure 5. The pressure drop is related to the space velocity (volumetric flow rate / volume of the sample), as the volume of the samples is different. The ratio pressure drop : space velocity gives us a possibility of a direct comparison of these particular filters for use in vehicles.

Each of the samples was analysed using scanning electron microscope (SEM) or X-ray tomography (XRT). These images are shown in the Figure 6. Porosimetry was also measured for each sample. The results are arranged in the Table 2.

Figure 6: Images of AT sample from SEM (left), cordierite sample (center) and SiC sample (right) from XRT.

Table 2: Porosimetry of samples

	aluminium titanate	cordierite	silicon carbide
porosity (%)	58	63	57
pore diameter (μm)	15	23	19

Conclusions

By series of measurements, it was ascertained that the cordierite filter provides the lowest pressure drop, while the AT provides the greatest one. We can explain this by the fact that the cordierite filter contains the greatest pores and its porosity is the highest as well. This means the lowest pressure drop caused by flow through the wall.

The cordierite sample is also the shortest one, which causes the lowest Darcy's pressure drop, generated by friction along the channels.

This study provided a set of data, which will be used to assemble a mathematical model describing behavior of gases in different particulate filter. These models may be used for developing new DPFs for either cars, trucks or buses and thus contribute to more effective and eco-friendly operation of these vehicles.

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List of Abbreviations

AT	aluminium titanate
DPF	diesel particulate filter
HC	hydrocarbons
MFC	mass flow controller
SEM	scanning electron microscop
XRT	X-ray tomography

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